
THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY

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KEYWORDS

Digital economy, Developed countries, Information technology, Economic indicator, Technology infrastructure

ABSTRACT

In this article you can get the following information about digital economy: "Brief information about digital economy", "Advantages of digital economy", "Disadvantages of digital economy", "Digital economy based on developed countries", "Digital economy in Uzbekistan ways of development".

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RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI O'RNI

KALIT SO'ZLAR:

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ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada siz raqamli iqtisodiyot haqida quyidagi ma'lumotlarni olishingiz mumkin. "Raqamli iqtisodiyot haqida qisqacha malumot", "Raqamli iqtisodiyotning afzalliklari", "Raqamli iqtisodiyotni salbiy tomonlari", Rivojlangan davlatlar asosida raqamli iqtisodiyot", "O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'llari".

So'ngi vaqtlarda "Digital Economy" tushunchasi juda ko'p marotaba ishlatilmoqda. Darhaqiqat, ko'plab rivojlangan mamlakatlarda digital economy ularning rivojlanishiga sezilarli darajada ta'sir o'tqazmoqda.

Keling avvalo "Digital Economy" kelib chiqishi tarixini o'rganaylik.

Digital Economy bu uzoq vaqtlar oldin ya'ni 1995-yil Massachusetts universiteti amerikalik olim Nikolas Negroponte tomonida aniqlab berilgan. Olim axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini intensiv rivojlanishini ortidan eski iqtisodiyotni yangi iqtisodiyotga o'tishda qanday o'zgarishlar ro'y berishi mumkinligini aytib bergan.

Digital Economy - bu xo'jalik faoliyatini yuritish bo'lib, bunda ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatishdagi asosiy omili raqamlar ko'rinshidagi ma'lumotlar bo'lib, katta hajmdagi axborotlarni qayta ishlash va shu qayta ishlash natijasini analiz qilish yordamida har xil turdagi ishlab chiqarish, xizmat ko'rsatish, texnologiyalar, qurilmalar, saqlash, mahsulotlarni yetkazib berishda oldingi tizimdan samaraliroq yechimlar tadbiiq qilishdir. Boshqacha qilib aytgancha, raqamli iqtisodiyot bu onlayn xizmatlar ko'rsatish, elektron tulovlar amalga oshirish, internet savdo va boshqa turdagi sohalarni raqamli kompyuter texnologiyalarini rivojlanishi bilan bog'langan faoliyat. Digital Economy raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan, elektron biznes va elektiron tijorat bilan bog'langan, raqamli tova va xizmatlar ishlab chiqarayotgan va taqdim etilayotgan iqtisodiy xizmat va tovarlar uchun hisob-kitoblar elektron pul orqali amalga oshiriladigan iqtisodiyfaolyatdir.

Axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlanishi va tadbiiq qilinishi evaziga kundalik hayotimizda juda ko'plab qulayliklar paydo bo'lmoqda.

Developed countries are countries that have transitioned to a digital economy.

Bulardan AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Daniya, Finlandiya, Singapur, Janubiy Korya, Gonkong, Norvegiya, Shvetsiya va Shvetsariya kiradi.

Tajribalar natijasida digital economy rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan davlatlarda teng huquqli qoidalarini, o'yinning barcha ishtirokchilari uchun bir xil imkoniyat beradi. Demak, digital economy rivojlanishi uchun davlat hamma uchun teng sharoit yaratib berishi, iloji boricha bozor qonun-qoida shartnomalar shaffof bo'lishi, qonunlar bozor talabidan kelib chiqqan holda (ya'ni bozordagi rivojlanish tendensiyalarini oldindan aniqlay olishi va kerakli normativ hujjatlarni qabul qilishi) o'yin ishtirokchilari uchun erkinlik berishi

zarurdir.

Zamonaviy ilm-fanning cho'qqisi yuqori texnologiyalarda, raqamli olamda ko'zga tashlanadi. Zero, digital economy aql bovar qilmas katta hajmda raqamli ma'lumotlarni to'plashda va to'la qonli taqdim etishni davom etmoqda. 2022-yilda global IP trafik hajmi 150 700 Gbit/s (solishtirish uchun 2017-yil 45 000 Gbit/s) chiqishi ko'zda tutilayotgandi. Shuningdek texnologiya olamida ko'pchilikka ma'lum bo'lgan "Microsoft" korporatsiyasi asoschisi Bill Geytsning bir fikiri bor. "Tez orada Yer sharida faqat ikki tur kompaniyalari mavjud bo'ladi. Birinchisi, internet orqali biznes qiluvchi va ikkinchisi, biznesdan chiqqan kompanyalardir".

Xususan Digital Economy afzalliklari va salbiy tomonlari haqida to'xtaladigan bo'lsak.

Albatta, Information technology texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi, zamonaviy texnologiyalarning hayotimizga tadbiiq etilishi har bir inson hayotida ko'plab ijobiy imkoniyatlar berishi mumkin. Raqamli texnologiyalar rivojlanishi ortidan inson, unga kerakli xizmatdan tezroq foydalanishi, internet orqali o'ziga kerakli mahsulotlarni arzon sotib olish bilan ko'plab pul mablag'larini tejash mumkin.

Shuningdek information technology quyidagi afzalliklarni berish mumkin:

- ishlab chiqarishda mehnat samaradorligini oshirish
- ishlab chiqarishdagi harajatlarni kamayishi
- kompaniyalarning raqobatdoshligini o'sishi
- yangi ish o'rnini yaratilishi
- yangi zamonaviy kasblar paydo bo'lishi
- kambag'allikni yengishni yangicha usuli

Bu raqamli iqtisodiyotni bor yo'g'i bir nechta afzalliklaridir.

Digital Economy rivojlanishini bizning kundalik hayotimizga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi, oddiy foydalanuvchiga ko'plab qo'shimcha imkoniyatlar beradi va qolaversa bozorni o'sishi va rivojlanishini ta'minlab berish mumkin.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot keltirib chiqarishi mumkin bo'lgan xavflardan

birinchi o'rinda Kiber hujum xavfidir. Bunda asosan shaxsiy xujjatlarni va shaxsiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy xuquqlarini oshkor qilish kabi mommlarni amalga oshiradi.

Axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalarini rivojlantirishda digital economy alohida faolyat turini emas, balki ishbilarmonlik, sanoat obyektlari, xizmatlarda axborot texnologiyalardan faol foydalanishni anglatada. Agar oddiy iqtisodiyotda moddiy buyumlar asosiy resurs hisoblansa, raqamli iqtisodiyotda bu qayta ishlanadigan hamda uzatiladigan axborot, ma'lumotlar bo'ladi.

Nufuzli xalqaro tashkilotlar olib borgan tahlillarga ko'ra digital economy yalpi ichki mahsulotni kamida 30 foizga oshiradi, shuningdik xufyona iqtisodiyotga barha beradi.

O'zbekistonda "Raqamli O'zbekiston-2030" dasturini ishlab chiqilishi va hayotga tatbiiq etilishi, eng avvalo, puxta va mukammal tashkiliy-huquqiy mexanizmlarni shakllantirish, qolaversa, innovatsion g'oyalar, texnologiyalar va ishlanmalarni joriy etish bo'yicha davlat organlari va tadbirkorlik subyektlarining uzviy hamkorligini ta'minlash,

barcha soha va tarmoqlarda ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatishni raqamli texnologiyalar bilan qamrab olish, bu borada zamonaviy bilimlarni chuqur egallagan, intellektual salohiyatli kadrlarni yetishtirish, shu orqali, mamlakatda "axborotlashgan jamiyat" muhitini yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa: Aql-zakovat va ilm — taraqqiyot qanotidir. Zamonaviy ilm-fanning cho'qqisi yuqori texnologiyalarda, raqamli olamda ko'zga tashlanadi. To'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi taraqqiyotning yangi ko'rinishi—"Digital Economy" boshlangani anglatadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Uchkun S., Dilshod N. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING THE SIGNIFICANT ACCOUNTS IN THE REVENUE CYCLE //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 32-36.
2. Dilshod N. XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA KORXONALARDA TUSHUMLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL QILISH BOSQICHLARI VA DASTAKLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 105-110.
3. Najmiddinov D. R., Shodlikov D. E. THE EFFECT OF THE SECRET ECONOMY IN A DAILY LIFE OF THE SOCIETY //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1A. – C. 56-59.
4. G'aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O 'ZBEKISTONDA ISTE'MOL SAVATCHASI HOZIRGI HOLATINI VA UNI SHAKILLANTIRISH YO 'NALISHLARI //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 119-125.
5. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 634-635.
6. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 151-156.
7. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАСHTИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 2. – C. 139-142.
8. Xaydarov B. IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION ON THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 163-174.
9. Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich, Xudayarov Rashid Tuychiyevich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT BIZNESNI REJALASHTIRISH. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 110–113. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/130>
10. Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich, & Saitov Sirojiddin Abduvalievich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNESNING O'RNI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 113–116. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/131>

11. Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA BUXGALTERIYA VA AUDITNI O'RNI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 128–131. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/135>
12. Tuychieva Nodira, Baxrom Xaydarov, & Quziboyev Zafar. (2022). THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPETITION AND MONOPOLY IN THE ECONOMY. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(11), 241–245. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/324>
13. Baxrom Xaydarov. (2022). IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION ON THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(11), 163–174. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/317>.
14. Xolmuradovich X. B., Sherzod oqli A. Z., Rasulbek oqli K. J. BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINING TURLARI VA SHAKLLARINING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 18. – C. 140-145.
15. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. " YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING O 'ZARO MUTANOSIBLIGI MASALALARI //PEDAGOG. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 81-85.
16. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. 2022-2026-YILLARDA MO'LJALLANGAN YANGI O'ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOT STRATEGIYASINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI ISLOH QILISHIDAGI O'RNI //PEDAGOG. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 78-80.
17. Tuychieva N., Xaydarov B., Rashidova G. MONEY-CREDIT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 246-250.
18. Saitov Sirojiddin, Tuychieva Nodira, & Saydullayeva Dinora. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF PRICE AND FORMATION. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(11), 265–270. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/329>
19. Saitov Sirojiddin, & Achilov Azizbek. (2022). TRANSITION TO THE MARKET ECONOMY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(11), 255–258. Retrieved from <http://www.ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/327>
20. Sirojiddin S., E'zoza D., Abror E. THEORIES OF PERFECT AND IMPERFECT COMPETITION //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 1414-1434.
21. Saitov S., Mahliyo R., Aziza M. DIGITAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF ECONOMIC SYSTEMS IN OUR COUNTRY //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 1442-1462.

22. Sirojiddin S. POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING WORLD EXPERIENCE OF ORGANIZING FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 1388-1413.
23. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 10. – C. 185-191.
24. Nizametdinov A., Ahmedova H. Elektron ta'lim metodologiyasi rivojlantirishning usullari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 29-31.
25. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AGRAR SOHANING USTUVORLIGI UNDA INNOVATSIYALARNING QULLANISHI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 96–98. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/104>
26. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AGRAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR QO'LLASH USTUVORLIGI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 58–60. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/96>
27. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 251-254.
28. Akramovich N. A. et al. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI O'ZBEKISTONDAGI O'RNI //Conferencea. – 2022. – C. 67-69.
29. Nizametdinov Ali Akramovich. (2022). SUN'IY INTELEKTNI KADRLAR SIYOSATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 251–253. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/171>
30. Bahodirovna D. L., Rakhimovna R. T., Vladimirovna S. L. SPECIAL MEANS OF IMPROVING PHYSICAL PREPAREDNESS FOR SHORT DISTANCE RUNNERS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – C. 95-99.
31. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE NATURE, CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES OF THE HIDDEN ECONOMY AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 22-39.
32. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN OUR DAILY LIFE //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – C. 100-124.
33. Akramovich N. A. et al. PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN WORKING WITH THE POPULATION IN THE BANKING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 25-30.

34. Alijon N., Sherzod Y. FACTORS OF INSURANCE ACTIVITY IMPLEMENTATION //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 20-24.
35. Nizametdinov Ali Akramovich. (2022). HISTORY, SUBJECT AND OBJECT OF FORMATION OF "MACROECONOMICS". Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(1), 209–210. Retrieved from <https://giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/998>
36. Rashid X., Mokhichekhra B. The Actions of International Economic Organizations to Solve Global Issues //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – T. 14. – C. 109-118.
37. Khudoyarov R. IMPROVING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN A MARKET ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 2. – C. 610-612.
38. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. BIG DATA TYPES OF EDUCATION SYSTEM AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING THEM IN THE FIELD //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 21-24.
39. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 155-164.
40. Yusufjon A. DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 03. – C. 5-8.
41. Azimov Y. H. et al. Olympism and olympic education at the present stage //Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в современном мире. – 2016. – №. 13-4. – C. 119-121.
42. Muxtarov B. ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF POPULATION INCOME GROWTH IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 30-39.
43. Mukhtarov B. A. et al. Manifestation of Corruption in Society //Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 14. – C. 156-166.
44. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 634-635.
45. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 151-156.
46. Sirojiddin S., Nodira T., Dinora S. CHARACTERISTICS OF PRICE AND FORMATION //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 265-270.

47. Nodira T., Sirojiddin S., Azizbek Z. SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEMS //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 260-264.
48. Sirojiddin S., Azizbek A. TRANSITION TO THE MARKET ECONOMY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 255-258.
49. Xolmuradovich X. B., Abduvalievich S. S. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNESNING O 'RNI //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 113-116.
50. Saitov S., Mahliyo R., Aziza M. DIGITAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF ECONOMIC SYSTEMS IN OUR COUNTRY //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1442-1462.
51. Sirojiddin S., E'zoza D., Abror E. THEORIES OF PERFECT AND IMPERFECT COMPETITION //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1414-1434.
52. Sirojiddin S. POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING WORLD EXPERIENCE OF ORGANIZING FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1388-1413.
53. Сайтов С. А., Хайдаров Б. Х. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МЕТОДА «SWOT-АНАЛИЗ» В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 150-153.
54. То'uchiyeva N. Elektron Ta 'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 40-41.
55. Норбеков Х., Туйчиева Н. Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 589-592.
56. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PRONUNCIATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SCHOOL STUDENTS //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
57. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IS BASED ON THE JAPANESE EXPERIENCE //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 205-208.
58. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.
59. Nodira T. INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 346-351.

60. Nodira T. PRIORITIES FOR ORGANIZING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 192-199.
61. To'ychiyeva N. AGRAR TARMOQDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING TASHKILIIY-IQTISODIY ASOSLARI //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 3-6.
62. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION IN GRADES 1-4» //РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ. – С. 1133.
63. To'ychiyeva N. THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 103-105.
64. To'ychiyeva N. AGRAR SOHADA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 53-56.
65. Sirojiddin S., Nodira T., Dinora S. CHARACTERISTICS OF PRICE AND FORMATION //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 265-270.
66. Nodira T., Kudratbek N. DEVELOP ANTI-MONOPOLISM AND COMPETITION ESSENTIALLY, ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1243-1258.
67. Nodira T., Jushkunbek X. THE ROLE AND PLACE OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS IN SOLVING GLOBAL ISSUES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1176-1190.
68. Nodira T., Bibixonim S. DIFFERENT FORMS OF PROPERTY //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1221-1235.
69. Nodira T., Nodir M. LABOR FORCE, ITS EMPLOYMENT AND UNEMPLOYMENT //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1191-1205.
70. Nodira T., Shukrullo A. TYPES OF MARKETING AND ITS CONTENT //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 1206-1220.